

A direct spectrophotometric method for the determination of mercury in environmental and biological samples using *p*-carboxybenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene

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Abstract : A very simple, sensitive and highly selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of mercury in biological and environmental samples described herewith is based on the formation of orange coloured species of Hg^{II} with *p*-carboxybenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene (CDABAB) and a non-ionic surfactant TX-100 over pH range 9.4–10.6. The orange colored Hg^{II}-(TX-100)-(CDABAB) complex in aqueous medium shows maximum absorbance at 510 nm with molar absorptivity value of $7.9 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The detection limit of the method is 6 ng ml⁻¹. The system obeys Beer's law up to 2.0 μg Hg^{II} ml⁻¹ in aqueous phase. The repeatability of the method was checked by finding relative standard deviation (RSD, *n* = 10) value for solutions each containing 1.0 μg Hg^{II} ml⁻¹ and RSD value of the method was found to be 1.5%. The validity of the method has been satisfactorily examined for the determination of mercury in biological and environmental samples. The RSD value for the actual analyte content ranged between 2.1 to 2.7%.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, mercury, substituted azobenzene.

Mercury being one of the most toxic heavy metals its determination in variety of samples at trace levels is of great importance. For many years most of the mercury determinations in various environmental samples have been carried out by atomic absorption spectrophotometer^{1,2}, graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrophotometer³, electro thermal atomic absorption spectrophotometer⁴, cold vapor atomic absorption spectrophotometer^{5,6}, flow injection-cold vapor-atomic absorption spectrophotometer⁷, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry^{8,9}, reversed-phased high performance liquid chromatography¹⁰, and voltammetry¹¹. These techniques although offer low detection limits, however, high maintenance cost initial equipment cost and requirement of skilled personnel are the major demerits.

Many spectrophotometric methods for determination of mercury are reported such as diphenylthiocarbazon¹², dithiozone¹³, *N*-benzoyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine¹⁴, diethyl-dithiocarbamate¹⁵, [1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol]¹⁶, diphenylthiocarbazon¹⁷. These reagents are less sensitive and suffer from interferences of small amounts of ions such as Bi³⁺, As³⁺, Ag⁺, Sn⁴⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, In³⁺, Ni²⁺, Ga³⁺, V⁵⁺ and Co²⁺. Triphenyltetrazolium chloride¹⁸ and dye rhodamine 6G¹⁹, are reported to be sensitive reagents for spectrophotometric determination of Hg in spite of poor selectivity

Table 1. Comparison of the present method with other spectrophotometric methods for the determination of mercury(II)

Reagents	pH acidity	Analytical medium	λ_{max} (nm)	$\epsilon = \text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \times 10^4$	Remarks
<i>N</i> -Benzoyl- <i>N</i> -phenylhydroxylamine ^d	3.0–6.0	Chloroform	340	0.26	Poor sensitivity, Sb ⁴⁺ , Bi ³⁺ , As ³⁺ , W ⁶⁺ interfere
Diethyldithiocarbamate ^e	9.0	Aqueous	445	1.16	Poor sensitivity, Ag ⁺ , Bi ³⁺ , Sn ⁴⁺ interfere
[1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol] (PAN) ^f	9.0	Aqueous	555	2.03	Zn ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , In ³⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Ga ³⁺ interfere
Diphenylthiocarbazon ^d	0.5–3.0	Chloroform	490	2.05	V ⁵⁺ interfere
Diphenylthiocarbazon ^e	Acidic	1,4 Dioxane	488	2.5	Co ²⁺ interfere
Triphenyltetrazolium chloride ^f	1.0–9.0	Chloroform	255	6.45	λ_{max} at near UV Bi ³⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , SCN ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ interfere
Rhodamine 6G ^g	1.7	Aqueous	575	7.0	Cu ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Bi ³⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ interfere
<i>p</i> Carboxy-benzenediazoaminobenzene- <i>p</i> -azobenzene	9.5–10.5	Aqueous	510	7.9	Sensitive, selective and free from interference (Present method)

^aRef 14, ^bRef 15, ^cRef 16, ^dRef 17, ^eRef 12, ^fRef 18, ^gRef 19

The present paper deals with a simple, sensitive and highly selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of mercury in biological and environmental samples using *p*-carboxybenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene in presence of non-ionic surfactants (TX-100) proposed for the determination of mercury at trace levels by spectrophotometric. The characteristic features of some spectrophotometric methods reported earlier for determining mercury are presented in Table 1

Table 2. Effect of surfactant on the Hg^{II}-(CDABAB) complex system

Surfactant	Absence	Titon X-100	Tween-80	Tween-20	Brij-35	CPC	SDS
λ_{max} (nm)	510	510	510	510	510	500	500
ϵ ($\times 10^4$)	4.21	7.9	6.8	6.2	5.9	0.42	1.6
$dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$							

CPC (Cetylpyridinium chloride) SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfonate)

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of Hg^{II}-(TX-100)-(CDABAB) complex shows maximum absorbance at 510 nm against reagent blank at 10.0 pH. The reagent blank exhibits appreciable absorption in this region and therefore it was used as reference for all absorbance measurements, Fig 1

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Hg^{II}-(TX-100)-(CDABAB) complex and the reagent blank (a) the Hg^{II}-(TX-100)-(CDABAB) complex, against the reagent blank, (b) the reagent blank against distilled water

The formation of orange coloured complex is maximum between pH 9.4–10.6. Above and under this interval the complexation decreases. Therefore, pH 10.0 was kept constant throughout the experiment by using NaOH-H₃BO₃ buffer.

The constant and maximum colour of the complex was achieved, when the concentration of *p*-carboxybenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene in the final aqueous solution was varied between (1.45–3.48) $\times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³. Hence, the further investigation was carried out at 2.90 $\times$

10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ *p*-carboxybenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene throughout the experiment

The effect of surfactants on the Hg^{II}-(CDABAB) complex were studied. The result (Table 2) showed that both in the presence of surfactants, anionic surfactants or cationic surfactants, the Hg^{II}-(CDABAB) complex gives a low absorption, whereas in the presence of nonionic surfactants, the absorption of the chromogenic system increases markedly. Various nonionic surfactants enhance the absorbance in the following sequence TX-100 > Tween 80 > Tween 20 > Brij-35. Experiments showed that TX-100 is the best additive. The studies on the effect of concentration of TX-100 indicated that a concentration range of (1.23–2.48) $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ TX-100 solution was sufficient for maximum colour development of Hg^{II}-(TX-100)-(CDABAB) complex. Therefore, 1.86 $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ TX-100 solution was kept constant throughout the experiment.

Table 3. Tolerable amount of diverse ions in the determination of 1.0 μ g Hg^{II} ml⁻¹

Ions added	Tolerable amount ^a (μ g ml ⁻¹) aqueous phase
Ni ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺	25
V ⁵⁺ , Zn ²⁺	50
Be ²⁺ , W ⁶⁺	75
Fe ³⁺ , Sb ³⁺ , Sn ⁴⁺	100
Ca ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺	150
Bi ³⁺ , Cr ⁶⁺ , Co ²⁺	200
Mg ²⁺ , Se ⁴⁺	250
As ³⁺	600
Al ³⁺ , PO ₄ ³⁻	1100
F ⁻ , Br ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻	1200
K ⁺	1500
Cl ⁻ , SCN ⁻	1600
Na ⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻	2000

^aIons were considered to interfere when they caused change in complex absorbance by $\pm 2\%$

The temperature of the aqueous solution should be at the normal in room temperature. There was found to be no change in absorbance of the complex. All experiment work was carried out at room temperature.

The system obeyed Beer's law up to 2.0 μ g Hg^{II} ml⁻¹ with an excellent linearity in terms of correlation coefficient value of 0.997. The molar absorptivity of the Hg^{II}-(TX-100)-(CDABAB) complex, calculated in terms of Hg^{II}, is 7.9 $\times 10^4$ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at λ_{max} 510 nm. The precision of the method in terms of relative standard deviation (*n* = 10) for the determination of 1.0 μ g Hg^{II} ml⁻¹ is 1.5%. In this method the detection limit, defined as for photometry, the concentration of analyte causing more absorbance than

twice the standard deviation of blank absorbance ($n = 10$) at 95% probability of Hg is 6 ng ml^{-1} .

The effect of various diverse ions on the determination of $1.0 \text{ }\mu\text{g}$ of Hg^{II} ml^{-1} was studied. The Hg^{II} concentration was kept fixed while that of the concentrations of various foreign ions causing possible interference was varied. The method is found to be free from the interference of most of the foreign species, Table 3.

Fig. 2. Curve fitting method for the determination of molar ratio of mercury to : (a) *p*-carboxybenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene (CDABAB), (b) TX-100. $C_{\text{Hg}} = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $C_{\text{CDABAB}} = 2.90 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $C_{\text{TX-100}} = 1.86 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The composition of the mercury complex was determined by the curve fitting method. The molar ratio of metal to CDABAB, TX-100 was determined by plotting logarithmic value of distribution ratio of metal $[\log \{A_{\text{eq}}/(A_{\text{max}} - A_{\text{eq}})\}]$ where, A_{max} = maximum absorbance of the complex at λ_{max} under optimum reagent concentration at a level of $1.0 \text{ }\mu\text{g}$ Hg^{II} ml^{-1} ; A_{eq} = absorbance of Hg^{II} complex at equilibrium with different known concentrations of reagents viz. CDABAB/TX-100 versus logarithmic values of varied known concentrations of CDABAB/TX-100 in aqueous solution.

The structure indicated a 1 : 2 ratio of mercury to CDABAB complex.

The inclination of the curves for CDABAB was found to be very close to integer 2 in case of CDABAB and 1 for TX-100. Thus, a 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratio complex of Hg^{2+} : CDABAB : TX-100 was predicted. Fig. 2 indicates the metal-ligand ratio of the CDABAB and TX-100. The probable reaction mechanism can be shown as given below : $\text{Hg}^{2+} + 2(\text{CDABAB}) + \text{TX-100} \leftrightarrow [\text{Hg}(\text{CDABAB})_2 \cdot \text{TX-100}]$.

Experimental

A Systronics VIS-spectrophotometer type-106 was used for absorbance measurement. A Systronics digital pH meter type 335 was employed for the measurement of pH of solutions. A Samsung, India microwave radiation equipment, model-CE2877L was employed for digesting the samples.

All chemicals used were of analytical-reagent grade or the highest purity available. Double distilled water and absolute ethanol were used throughout. A standard stock Hg^{II} solution ($1000 \text{ }\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by dissolving 0.135 g of mercuric chloride in a small amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid followed by diluting with distilled water. Working standard solution was prepared by diluting the stock solution to appropriate volume. The synthesis of a new compound *p*-carboxybenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene was done by a method similar to that used for the preparation of cation²³ and *o*-carboxy-benzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene²⁴. Three gram of *p*-amino benzoic acid was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid followed by addition of 2 ml of aniline. The temperature was kept below $15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ then 1.5 g sodium nitrite and 30% sodium acetate was added. The precipitated dye was filtered after 10–15 min and recrystallised from alcohol. The purity of the dye was checked by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using 1 + 5 methanol + butanol, which showed only one compound. The dye is stable for long period. A 0.1% (w/v) solution in ethanol was used as reagent. A $3.10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (2%, v/v) of TX-100 was prepared in double distilled water. A NaOH- H_3BO_3 buffer solution ($\approx \text{pH } 10.0$) was used for adjusting the pH of aqueous solution.

p-Carboxybenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene

Procedure : An aliquot (1.0 ml) of solution containing maximum up to $2.0 \text{ }\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Hg^{II} was taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask. The pH of the solution was adjusted at 10.0 ± 0.2 by addition of 2.0 ml borate buffer solution. Then 0.6 ml of 2.0%, TX-100 solution was added. To the above solution, 1.0 ml of 0.1% of CDABAB solutions in ethanol solution was mixed and the final volume was made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the complex against reagent blank was measured at λ_{max} 510 nm .

Sample preparation and analysis :

Environmental samples : Each filtered environmental water sample (100 ml) was mixed with 2 ml of 4.5 M sul-

phuric acid in a 500 ml distillation flask. The sample was digested in presence of excess potassium permanganate solution. The digested was transferred into a 50 ml calibrated flask and diluted up to the mark with distilled water. Water samples with known amounts of mercury (1.0 µg) added was analyzed by the present and the reported methods¹³, Table 4

Table 4. Analytical data for the determination of Hg^{II} in environmental and biological samples and chemical formulation and *F* and *t*-test data for analytical quality assurance

Samples	Added Hg ^{II} (µg ml ⁻¹)	Mercury(II)/µg ml ⁻¹		<i>F</i> _{cal} ^b	<i>t</i> _{cal} ^c
		Present method (N ₁ = 6)± ^a	Dithizone method (N ₂ = 5)± ^a		
Environmental samples					
River water ^d	1.0	1.03 ± 0.01	1.03 ± 0.01	0.91	0.97
Pond water ^e	1.0	1.05 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.01	0.06	0.53
Waste water ^f	1.0	1.08 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.01	0.32	0.35
Biological samples					
Blood serum	1.0	1.0 ± 0.1	0.97 ± 0.02	0.014	0.11
Urine	1.0	0.96 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	0.73	0.40
Chemical formulation					
Emusan-6	-	11.4 ± 0.7	11.5 ± 0.7	0.054	0.82

^aValues are means ± standard deviations

^bTabulated *F*-values at 95% confidence level is 6.26 for N₁ = 6, N₂ = 5 (i.e., for n₁ = N₁ - 1, 5 degrees of freedom, n₂ = 1, 4 degrees of freedom)

^cTabulated *t*-value at 95% confidence level is 2.262 for N₁ + N₂ = 11 (or n₁ = N₁ + N₂ - 2, 9 degrees of freedom)

^dKhaton river water, Raipur, Chhattisgarh

^ePond water Sukama, Bastar, Chhattisgarh

^fWaste water from coal mines area, Korba, Chhattisgarh

Biological samples. The method was also applied to the determination of mercury in blood and urine samples. Since the available samples contained no mercury, known amounts were added. A 1.0 ml of whole blood sample or 2.0 ml urine sample, 0.2 ml of perchloric acid and 0.5 ml of nitric acid were placed in high pressure micro wave acid-digestion bomb. The bombs were sealed tightly and then positioned in the carousel of the microwave oven. The system was operated for 5 min at 500 W. The digest was evaporated to near dryness. The dried blood residues were then dissolved in 5.0 ml of distilled water and filtered. An aliquot 1.0 ml of the final solution was pipetted into a 10 ml volumetric flask and the content of mercury was determined by the present and the reported methods¹³, Table 4

Fungicides: Methoxy ethyl mercury chloride (MEMC, Excel Industries Ltd, Mumbai), known as Emisan-6 is used as contact-fungicide against flag smut of wheat, black root of sugar beet, wet seed dressing before planting and other disease of cereals and cotton. A 5 mg/20 ml test solution of MEMC in ethanol was warmed to 70 °C for 10 min and

then test solution (8.0 ml) were analysed by the present and the reported methods¹³, Table 4.

Analytical quality assurance (AQA): The *F*-test²⁴ was performed at 95% probability to compare the result of the present method with that of the dithizone method¹⁶. Because in all cases the values of *F* (sd_1^2/sd_2^2) were less than the tabulated *F* values at the 95% confidence level, we conclude that there is no significant difference in the precision of the present and reported method. The *t*-test²⁴ was performed at 95% confidence level. Again, in all cases the calculated *t*-values were less than the tabulated values of *t*, indicating no statistical difference between the results obtained by the present method and the standard method. Thus, both the *F*-test shows a high degree of agreement between the values obtained by the present method and the standard method. Thus, both the *F*-test and *t*-test show a high degree of agreement between the values obtained by present method and the standard values of mercury(II), Table 4

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